

DIFFERENT APPROACHES TO DETERMINE THE ESSENCE OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCES OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract. *This article reflects different approaches to determining the nature of professional competencies of future primary school teachers.*

Keywords: *competence, modernization, competence of a teacher, motivational, orientational, assessment, operational, voluntary, psychological and pedagogical research, competence-based approach.*

Modernization of the education of the Republic of Uzbekistan includes changes in the professional and general education system in the logic of the competence approach. In addition, in accordance with the Concept of Modernization of Higher Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the main tasks of higher education are: to train a teacher who is competitive in the labor market, competent, responsible, who know his profession well, who can work effectively at the level of world standards in their specialty [1].

From the point of view of modernization of education, the requirement to train modern teachers in terms of quality is considered among the relevant areas of activity, which is confirmed by a review of specialized literature. Researches are being carried out on various areas of competence development of future teachers, and work is being carried out to study the content of the teacher's professional activity in our country and abroad.

Researchers studying the nature of pedagogical competences of teachers determine its multifaceted, diverse nature, according to them, the structure of pedagogical competence is contextual, that is, it has its own interpretations and is determined by different positions of the authors and may contain different components. Researchers distinguish the necessary competencies for a certain activity. Russian researchers: L.P. Alekseeva, A.S. Belkin, E.F. Zeer, N.V. Kuzmina, A.K. Markova, L.I. Mitina, L.A. Petrovsky, A.V. Khutorskoy and others contributed greatly to the development of the competence-based approach. In science, a number of scientists A.G. Bermus, N.F. Yefremova, I.A. Zimnyaya and others believe that competence is related to the formation of professional requirements for a specialist.

We also consider a specialist with competencies as the ability to independently perform professional activities. The professional activity of a specialist and the competence corresponding to this activity can be called professional competence.

In order to study the problem of teacher competence, we believe that it is appropriate to refer to some scientific-pedagogical studies on the readiness of specialists to work. M.I. Dyachenko, L.A. Kandybovich, specialists' readiness for action:

motivational (forming a stable attitude to activity, profession);

orientation (formation of knowledge and ideas about the characteristics and conditions of professional activity);

assessment (formation of the ability to self-assess the compliance of the process of performing professional tasks with acceptable work patterns);

operational (the process of acquiring the methods and techniques of professional activity, the necessary skills and qualifications);

voluntary (self-control, formation of the ability to manage the actions that make up the performance of work tasks) components.

Emergence of a new educational paradigm of "formation of a mature personality" in the educational process conducted in primary classes, informing the society cannot be realized without the formation of a competent specialist in the modern socio-economic conditions.

There are various approaches to determining the nature of professional competence in psychological and pedagogical research: person-oriented, competency-based, systematic, activity-based, etc. We may not consider all available approaches, but we will touch on some and try to clarify the complex nature of the concept of "competence".

The scientific works of A.V. Khutorskiy were used in the process of studying the competence-based approach in our research. According to him, the modernization of education, the direction associated with this approach "... unites the personal and social meaning of competence-based education."

We understand competence as a person's ability to perform a particular type of professional activity. Competence is the ability of a person to perform a particular type of professional activity as well. Therefore, competence in our research is considered as a set of certain competencies. A.V. Khutorskiy's approach makes it possible to form information and communication competence in the training of students and future primary school teachers as a result of the educational process [2].

Although the concept of "Competency-based approach" is a new notion in pedagogy, this concept has become widespread in the last decades of the 20th century. As a methodological basis for the emergence of the term "Competency-based approach" based the concept of teacher training in higher education in the USA in the early 70s of the XX century. The evaluation of the teacher's competence is based on the measurement of three main directions: "knowing, performing and checking" and includes not only the identification of basic skills, but also the analysis of conceptual knowledge and pedagogical skills.

D.A. Ivanov's theory "competency-based approach is an approach focused on the educational result, and the result is not the amount of information learned, but the ability of a person to act in various problem situations" occupies an important place in the study of the concept of competence approach [3].

This approach is characterized by the recognition of educational results as important outside the educational system, and this implies a change in the units of educational content organization and methods of evaluating the effectiveness of the educational process (quality assessment).

According to V.V. Serikov and V.A. Bolotov, the competence-based approach is not for marking the level of knowledge, but it assesses the student's understanding of real events, mastering the ability to use modern techniques and technologies, moral standards, evaluation of one's own actions, practical tasks in the implementation of social roles of a citizens, legal norms and administrative structures, aesthetic assessment, career choice and assessment of readiness to study at a vocational educational institution, as well as to find a place in the labor market, to solve their own problems: forms the ability to solve existing problems, such as defining a life position, choosing a lifestyle, and ways to resolve conflicts [4].

The modern development of ICT makes it possible to use these technologies in almost all spheres of human activity. The scope of these technologies is constantly expanding. For this reason, we believe that the information-communicative competence provided by V.A. Bolotov helps the specialist to effectively solve problems in all types of activities.

A distinctive feature of learning based on the competence-based approach is that it is not "ready-made knowledge" offered by someone, but "the conditions for mastering this knowledge are sought" [5].

It can be assumed that students themselves form concepts based on research and learning activities necessary to solve problems. With such an approach, educational activity periodically acquires a research or practice-transformational character and becomes an assimilation science. An important feature of professional competence is that, firstly, it is manifested in activity, and secondly, it is focused on the future, despite its implementation nowadays [6].

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